

Effects of anionic surfactants on the kinetics of acidic hydrolysis of acetohydroxamic acid

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Manuscript received 20 May 2010, accepted 03 June 2010

Abstract : The acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of acetohydroxamic acid (AHA) in nitric acid solution has been studied spectrophotometrically in absence and presence of anionic surfactants, i.e. sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonic acid (SDBS), lithium dodecyl sulphate (LDS) and sodium 1-octane sulphonic acid (SOS). The variation of the rate constant with respect to the increasing concentration of anionic surfactant was examined. It was observed that the anionic surfactants accelerate the rate of reactions for hydrolysis of AHA in nitric acid. Activation parameters have also been determined.

Keywords : Kinetic study, acetohydroxamic acid, nitric acid, surfactants, activation parameters.

Introduction

Hydroxamic acids are naturally occurring compounds of great importance in analytical, biological, and medicinal fields, which are used as drug delivery systems, enzyme inhibitors, iron transport and DNA cleavage agents^{1,2}. These compounds have been used as excellent spectrophotometric and gravimetric reagents, with current interest focused on their reduction/complexation chemistry with metals^{3,4}. The simple hydroxamic acid, acetohydroxamic acid (AHA) (I) is a salt free, hydrophilic organic compounds RCONHOH, where R = CH₃, which act as bidentate O,O donor ligands and hence have higher affinities for hard cations⁵ such as Fe³⁺, Np⁴⁺ and Pu⁴⁺. On the basis of this interaction, numerous microorga-nisms developed hydroxamate type metal sequestering siderophores for the uptake, storage and transport of metal ions with biological relevance⁶⁻⁸. Recently, increasing interest in hydroxamic acids has been attributed, in part, to their application to nuclear fuel processing⁹⁻¹¹. Acetohydroxamic acid (AHA) is utilized as drug for hepatic coma and DNA scission agent. In addition to the reduction and complexation ability of AHA, it is also noteworthy to mention that under acidic conditions, AHA is unstable and undergoes hydrolysis¹²⁻¹⁵. The acidic hydrolysis of AHA is an irreversible destructive process resulting in formation of acetic acid and hydroxylamine

as degradation product.

Acetohydroxamic acid (AHA) (I)

Recently, increasing interest in micellar reaction media have attracted considerable attention as means of controlling the rate of reactions that are chemical, industrial and biological interest^{16,17}. In most cases, simple electrostatic considerations suffice for reactions are catalyzed by anionic surfactant. Anionic surfactant which accelerate reaction between hydrophobic substrates and cations (notably acid hydrolysis in which the reactive cation is H⁺) have been used in relatively few detailed studies¹⁸. Hence, the kinetic studies have been done in the presence of anionic micellar media.

A literature survey indicates that there are not many kinetic studies on the reaction of AHA in nitric acid in micellar media¹⁹⁻²³. Hence in the present investigation, we have used different anionic surfactants viz. sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonic acid (SDBS), lithium dodecyl sulphate (LDS) and sodium 1-octane sulphonic acid (SOS) for the study of hydrolysis reaction of acetohydroxamic acid in the presence of nitric acid. Activation parameters have also been calculated.

Results and discussion

Kinetics for the hydrolysis of AHA in the absence of surfactants : The kinetics of the hydrolysis of AHA was followed spectrophotometrically by following the decrease in the characteristic absorption of the Fe^{III}-AHA complex. The reaction followed pseudo-first order kinetics :

$$\begin{aligned}
 -d/dt [\text{AHA}] &= k [\text{AHA}] [\text{H}^+] \\
 &= k_{\Psi} [\text{AHA}] \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $k_{\Psi} = k [\text{H}^+]$

Acetic acid and hydroxylamine were the products of the hydrolysis. The experimental pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{Ψ} for the investigated reactions in non-micellar solutions were presented in Table 1. Measurement of the acid hydrolysis of AHA was made at different concentration of HNO₃. The first order constants increased linearly with increasing acid concentration (Fig. 1). The dependency of rate constant on the acid concentrations are linear function at a constant [AHA] = 0.01 M, this relationship indicates that the reaction is first-order with respect to AHA.

Hydroxamic acids are hydrolyzed through a mechanism in which the hydronium ion is transferred in the transition state and the reactions are specifically catalyzed by hydrogen ions catalyzed. In the simplest des-

Table 1. Rate constants of the hydrolysis reactions of aceto-hydroxamic acid with varying concentration of nitric acid at different temperatures

[HNO ₃] (M)	Temp. (°C)	$k_{\Psi} \times 10^{-3}$ (s ⁻¹)	k (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.5	27	1.02	2.00
	37	3.90	7.80
	47	7.60	15.2
	57	18.0	46.8
1.0	27	2.30	21.0
	37	8.70	8.70
	47	15.8	15.8
	57	38.0	56.7
2.0	27	4.40	2.30
	37	15.5	77.5
	47	35.0	18.7
	57	85.0	47.4
3.0	27	6.80	3.10
	37	27.5	9.10
	47	52.2	15.1
	57	130	33.4

Fig. 1. Rate acidity profiles for acid catalyzed hydrolysis of aceto-hydroxamic acid.

cription¹, the first step is a pre-equilibrium protonation and the second step is a rate determining attack of water on the hydrolysis of AHA starts with a rapid pre-equilibrium proton transfer (eq. (2)),

The carbon atom of the carbonyl group is then at-

tacked by water resulting in a tetrahedral intermediate. The carbonyl group is again created by the loss of a leaving group (eq. (3)),

Effects of anionic surfactants : The influence of anionic surfactants on the kinetic hydrolysis of AHA (0.01 M) has been studied with the fixed concentration of HNO_3 (0.5 M) at 47 °C. The data are shown in Table 2. Table 2 shows different anionic surfactants, SDS, SDBS, LDS, sodium 1-octane sulphonate (SOS) and their kinetic

Table 2. Kinetic rate data for alkaline hydrolysis of aceto-hydroxamic acid for anionic surfactant

[Surfactant] (mM)	$10^{-3} k_{\text{obs}} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	[SDS]	[SDBS]	[LDS]	[SOS]
0.0	7.60	7.60	7.60	7.60
1.7	10.8	9.00	9.80	9.80
3.4	13.5	10.6	10.9	11.2
6.9	10.2	8.45	12.2	13.0
13.8	7.60	3.50	7.00	11.0
20.8	6.50	1.30	4.10	8.90

rate effect. The concentration of the anionic surfactants, SDS, SDBS and sodium 1-octane sulphonate (SOS) used were in the range of (0.0017–0.0208 M). First order rate constants increase with increasing anionic surfactant (Fig. 2) concentration, goes through a maxima and then decreases, still higher concentration of SDS, SDBS, LDS and sodium 1-octane sulphonate (SOS). Iglesias *et al.*^{16,20} observed similar rate acceleration in the acid cata-

Fig. 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the acid hydrolysis of AHA as a function of increasing anionic surfactant concentrations.

lyzed hydrolysis of some esters. A micelle offers several binding sites for substrate; these include the hydrophobic core and hydrophobic binding sites located in the Stern layer. The Stern layer is particularly flexible in binding molecules as it contains the highly hydrophobic surfactant tails as well as water molecules. The negatively charged head groups facilitates the passage of H^+ ions of HNO_3 by means of electrostatic attraction in the Stern layer containing water soluble substrates thereby enhancing the rate of reaction. The rate increases gradually from SDS, SDBS, DLS and 1-octane sulphonate sodium salt in the Stern layer thereby lesser neutralization of charge and greater availability of protons occurs in the zone. The counter ions in such cases prefer to remain in the Gouy-Chapman layer. At low concentration of acid, the catalytic efficiency of surfactants is greater. By working at lower concentration of acid, strong catalyzing capacity of anionic surfactants is confirmed.

Kinetic hydrolysis of AHA in HNO_3 in the presence of anionic surfactants have been studied. The values obtained for the Na^+/H^+ indicates that the two cations have similar affinities for the micellar surface. This similarity suggests that competing protons are not in a state of higher charge density, but rather strongly hydrated. However the possibility of covalent bonding proton and surfactant cannot be ruled out without further investigation especially because such bonding has been suggested as an explanation for the rapid hydrolysis of micellized alkyl sulfates at higher acidity.

Effect of counterions : Added anionic surfactant increases the relative concentration of AHA and H^+ in the Stern layer and ascending branch of the curve is observed. At sufficient higher concentration of anionic surfactants increases more Na^+ and Li^+ ions are available in the Stern layer which in turn, competes with the concentration of H^+ ions. As a result, the rate of reaction at the specific sites in the Stern layer decreases. As the concentration of anionic surfactant increases, the observed rate constant initially increases and further decreases at higher concentration of anionic surfactant. Nevertheless, the micellar pseudo-first order condition confirms the dominant influence of the concentration effect, which is completely responsible for the observed rate acceleration in the presence of anionic surfactants.

Effect of temperature : Activation energy is higher in aqueous phase than micellar phase. To investigate whether differences of this kind between the state of the proton in water and the micellar phase might be responsible for the observed differences in the reaction rates, we studied the influence of temperature on the reaction rate in the presence and absence of anionic surfactants within temperature range at 47 to 57 °C. The activation parameters are presented in Table 3. A possible explanation of the difference in activation entropy between the non-micellar and micellar phases is that, the mobility of the transition state at the micellar surface is restricted by interaction

Table 3. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis of AHA

Surfactant	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Nil	76.0	-50.9	60.6	98.2
SOS	63.9	-85.2	49.3	76.9
DLS	54.3	-114.1	48.9	86.1
SDS	55.0	-118.2	48.0	86.5
SDBS	43.4	-153.8	48.9	99.0

between negative charged micelle sulfate heads and the positive charge of counterion. This restriction of mobility lowers the entropy of the transition state, but there is no parallel effect on the reagents or for the reaction in water. Hence the negative value of entropy of activation increases in the micellar media as compare to non-micellar media.

Conclusions :

The kinetics of the acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of acetohydroxamic acid in nitric acid solutions were studied spectrophotometrically in the absence and presence of anionic surfactants. The anionic surfactants accelerate the rate of reactions for hydrolysis of AHA in nitric acid. Anionic surfactant shows catalytic effect. Activation parameters were obtained at different temperature and observed energy of activation was higher in non-micellar phase than micellar phase.

Experimental

Materials : The acetohydroxamic acid was obtained from Sigma. The nitric acid was procured from Moly Chem and was used without further purification. The iron(III) chloride solution used in the spectrophotometri-

cal method was prepared by dissolution of anhydrous ferric chloride (SM, LR, 44 g) in triple distilled water (1 L) containing concentrated HCl (10 ml). The anionic surfactants, SDS, SDBS, LDS and sodium 1-octane sulphonic acid (SOS) were obtained by Sigma/Aldrich.

Method : The kinetics was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the concentration of the hydroxamic acid by the color reaction with Fe³⁺ ions. An aliquot of the reaction mixture (1 ml) was periodically removed and added to ferric chloride (2 ml) and the resulting solution was diluted to 6 ml and its absorbance were determined with a digital Systronics 104 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and Systronics 118 UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 500 nm. Beer's law was obeyed by the system.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor Rama Pande, Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India for providing laboratory facilities.

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